

Characteristics Of Entrepreneurs In The Traditional Market (Sore Market) Pamekasan In Central Pandemic Covid-19 Is Still Running

Mohammad Imam Sufiyanto¹, Shalehoddin²

¹²Madura State Islamic Institute (IAIN Madura), Pamekasan

Correspondent: Biologiyayan@gmail.com

Submitted : January 5, 2021 Revised : January 18, 2021 Published : January 23, 2021

Abstract: The communication model that is considered appropriate is to involve market managers as a source of credible messages, with messages containing the benefits and risks of revitalization which are effective in developing the motivation of traders and the media that allow direct responses from market players. This study aims to formulate a communication model to build change readiness for traditional market traders. The method used is a survey by interviewing 10 traditional market traders using a questionnaire instrument. The results showed that in the face of revitalization, traders are in a situation of uncertainty. All market elements, starting from the characteristics of traders, sources of messages, messages, and participatory communication, have a positive impact on traders' readiness with revitalization with a high entrepreneurial capacity of traders. Therefore, to build merchant readiness, the main thing that needs to be done is to build the entrepreneurial character of traders.

Keywords: entrepreneur character, traditional market, pandemic

1. Introduction

The entrepreneurial character of traders and the inadequate physical quality of traditional markets is a major problem in the development of traditional markets. The level of expertise and skills in maintaining good relationships with customers, low layout and cleanliness of goods sold, and inadequate conditions of traditional markets weaken the ability and competitiveness of traditional market traders.

This phenomenon also occurs in the city of Pamekasan. The condition of the old, shabby traditional market buildings as well as the arrangement of afternoon market traders so that they can unravel traffic jams are used as an excuse for the Pamekasan City Government to cooperate with private developers to rebuild several markets. However, the revitalization of traditional markets does not always go smoothly. The attraction of the community, traders, city government, and private developers have resulted in delays in the implementation of this revitalization. Traders think that the government is imposing its will for certain interests and does not pay attention to their aspirations.

Therefore, the phenomenon of rejection raises questions about, first, the communication approach was taken by market managers to build traders' readiness in facing revitalization. Readiness is shown by their belief, attitude, and interest in participating in revitalization

activities. Second, because the goal is to improve community welfare, revitalization is not only carried out by building or improving physical facilities, but also strengthening human resources, in this case, the entrepreneurial capacity of traders.

Based on these descriptions, the purpose of this study is to describe participatory communication to build entrepreneurial character and merchant readiness to face revitalization; and prove whether the characteristics of traders, message sources, message exposure, participatory communication, and environmental support affect traders' readiness to revitalize traditional markets. Third, find a communication model that can build entrepreneurial capacity and readiness of traders to face revitalization.

2. Research Method

This research was conducted using a survey approach and the data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential approaches. The location of the research was chosen purposively by considering that the object was chosen because it faced revitalization problems. The market studied in the city of Pamekasan is the Sore Market because this market belongs to the Pamekasan city government during the November 2020 research.

The population in this study included the traders in the market this afternoon, which amounted to around 510 traders. The number of samples is 10 people. Data analysis used, first, descriptive analysis to provide an overview of the communication carried out, and to test the relationship between variables using SEM through LISREL. The variables in this study consisted of (1) characteristics of traders, (2) credibility of message sources, (3) Breakthrough Message of Change.

3. Results and Discussion

Trader Characteristics

Trader characteristics are individual traits that are inherent in traders and related to aspects of life. And it can be seen that most of the respondents are in the quite old category (31-43 years). With this condition, it is hoped that they can get maximum results compared to those who are not productive. This is because the old age group is still productive and their age influences the decision-making process (Alfianita, et al, 2015). Older adults have to face many situations where decisions have financial consequences. Therefore, the age factor can affect an individual's readiness to change. The stereotype of older traders is usually unfavorable, and there is a broad bias that links decreased work productivity to age.

Education is the most important thing in a person's life, with education is, someone of productive age can compete in the job market. The higher the level of education the more time is provided for work. The higher more than level of education, the greater the tendency to work. This research also shows a real relationship between the entrepreneurial behavior of street vendors, age, formal education, non-formal education, business experience, and motivation.

They develop feelings of relative deprivation by comparing their current socio-economic conditions with their reference group, that is, individuals with the same level of education from other groups. Relative deprivation is a psychological condition that shows a person's dissatisfaction with the subjective gap or deficiency that he feels when he and his group are compared to other people or groups. Deprivation conditions can lead to perceptions of injustice. The research data also shows that most of the respondents' formal education is in the medium category. This condition illustrates a relatively high level of progress and resource capacity. Compared with less educated people, they are more likely to develop a feeling of missing something than those with higher education.

The trading experience provides additional expertise in running a business independently and the ability to measure the quality of information to increase understanding of the tangible benefits of new opportunities, accelerate business process creation, and improve performance. Experience can also increase confidence in an entrepreneur's ability to succeed (Simanjuntak, 2017). This means that it can strengthen one's intention to enter into new opportunities. The findings in this study indicate that traders who have high trading experience or more than 10 years of trading in the market have the highest percentage. This shows that market traders generally have trading experience which ultimately provides an adequate educational process to run a business.

Market Revitalization as Merchant Empowerment Efforts

In general, revitalization is interpreted as a process and method of reviving an area that is not functioning properly. Revitalization is carried out by increasing the vitality of the old area so that it can create a quality public area and increase the economic growth of the community around the revitalized area. From the perspective of market managers, market revitalization is an alternative to increase the empowerment of traders because market conditions are comfortable, clean, safe, and regular, market visitors increase so that traders' turnover also increases.

When the merchant's turnover increases, the merchant's profit will increase and the merchant's welfare will increase. For the increase in the number of buyers at kiosks in revitalized markets, it is higher than those that have not been revitalized. This difference is based on tests conducted at the 5% level, the results are significant. This shows that revitalization has increased the number of buyers in the market. However, the increase in the number of buyers did not significantly increase sales. The increase in sales of goods at revitalized market stalls was higher than for market stalls that had not been revitalized, however, the difference was not significant.

Apart from flyers, notice boards, and banners, market managers held at least three dialogues with traders. Dialogue with traders consists of two groups. The first group is a dialogue with directors of market management companies. Second, informally or in dialogue with the person in charge of each market management unit. Dialogue with the directors is carried out in a scheduled and planned manner, apart from involving individual traders, it also involves traders' organizations. Meanwhile, an informal dialogue is carried out without a plan (Muhidin, 2016: 50). This dialogue usually occurs whenever the two meet such as when the market manager at the unit level draws and collects monthly market fees and so on. There was also dialogue among traders so that information about revitalization reached traders who happened to be unable to attend the formal dialogue.

The results showed the low involvement of communication participants during the revitalization planning process. Almost all dimensions of participatory communication score low. The lowest score for the participatory communication dimension is on the level of feedback and mutual trust between market managers and traders. In dialogue, market managers get feedback from traders. However, some input from traders, according to traders, was not given enough attention. For example, a suggestion from traders that later after the market is revitalized they can occupy a kiosk as before the revitalization was rejected by the manager. Likewise, the question of the suggestion of the manager should not increase the retribution rate, because the rate is not balanced with the quiet market conditions. "... Market managers did not accept the proposal.

Participatory Communication of Market Managers and Traders

Market revitalization in the afternoon market was initiated by the Municipal Government of Pamekasan. The revitalization plan is disseminated through media channels in the form of leaflets, announcement boards, and banners in each market. Banners are placed in front of the market. Almost all traders are aware of the market revitalization plan, even though the announcement is only in front of the management office. In each meeting, traders ask the reasons for market revitalization. Market managers say that market revitalization is carried out to make the market more crowded, comfortable, and tidy. Therefore, traders see that the manager has genuine intentions. However, traders think that the managers are not yet open and provide complete information. For example, a socialization event illustrates the positive impact of revitalization. However, managers do not show any negative impact after the market is revitalized. For example, about the possibility of a decrease in sales if the market is revitalized (Meredith, 2018: 205).

Traders think that revitalization makes the market empty of visitors. This assumption arises from the experience of revitalizing the late afternoon market. After the revitalization, people are reluctant to shop at the afternoon market. There is a perception that if the market is revitalized the price of goods goes up. Especially as happened at the Afternoon Market which placed vegetable stalls and so on the second floor. "Buyers are reluctant to visit the new market (revitalization) because when shopping for their daily needs they have to go up to the second floor. Before being revitalized, sellers of foodstuffs and other daily necessities were on the ground floor so that buyers could easily reach them, said an afternoon market trader.

The results showed a low level of mutual trust between managers and traders. The lack of mutual trust between managers and traders is caused by the trader's experience. In the eyes of traders, market managers often break promises. This experience makes traders "suspect" the manager has his agenda. Apart from low mutual trust, the level of openness of each communication actor is also low. Openness is one of the factors that can increase trust. Numerous studies support this view. Found that managers who openly exchange ideas with employees can increase mutual trust between them.

Entrepreneurial Capacity

The results showed that the entrepreneurial capacity of traditional market traders as a whole had a moderate tendency. The show is that several characteristics of traders have a relationship with dimensions that support entrepreneurial capacities such as business insight, the courage to take risks, and responsiveness to opportunities. When viewed from a positive correlation, the low entrepreneurial capacity is due to the low time expansions, the cosmopolitan level of traders, capital, and merchant turnover. The results also show that entrepreneurial behavior is influenced by individual characteristics such as level of education, sufficient experience, and capital.

However, the results of this study indicate that age is negatively correlated with the courage to take risks and responsiveness to opportunities. This means that the older the trader is, the more reluctant he is to take risks such as losses and the less responsive he is to opportunities. That of there is a negative correlation between age and courage to take risks. Young entrepreneurs tend to have a strong desire to realize their own identity and achieve achievements through entrepreneurial activities, such as investing in new markets and launching new products. This also suggests that traders who are more senior or have high trading experience tend to be more cautious because of the lessons learned from their previous practices. This also explains that trading experience has a negative correlation with courage in taking risks.

Based on the interviews conducted, traders rely more on experience and rarely take part in business training. This reflects the passivity of traders in their efforts to increase their entrepreneurial capacity. The level of desire of traders to ask people who are considered to be able to improve their business performance is low. Likewise, the willingness to seek information through the mass media is also low. It is feared that this lack of information will have an impact on traders' lack of ability to analyze the situation around them.

An entrepreneurial capacity is a form of human capital that depends on the level of education, training, experience, and health. The results showed that the average formal education of the respondents was 8 years (equivalent to class II junior high school). This reflects the relatively low human capital of traders. Education is an investment that can provide benefits through work productivity. A person is said to have business insight if he can analyze and evaluate changes in the business environment, his strengths, and weaknesses. This ability affects the success of one's business. Low business insight causes traders to worry about changes including the entry of new competitors into their environment. Their inability to integrate information due to a lack of information makes them unable to react quickly and weakly predicts changes in the business environment. Because of that, they feel worried about their future condition.

Communication Model to Build Entrepreneurial Capacity and Traders' Readiness to Face Pandemic covid-19

It can be seen that the level of readiness of traders to change is low due to a pandemic. Traders have optimism during the pandemic, but the level of participation in revitalization is very low. In terms of participation in the meeting, according to information provided by a trader, if the issues raised are serious, such as an increase in fees, many traders are present (Scarborough, 2018: 305). However, when it comes to explaining the revitalization, many traders represent it to other people or the market association.

The results of this study indicate that directly the characteristics of traders, the credibility of market managers, messages of change, participatory communication, and environmental support have a positive effect on the quality of communication. This shows that building quality communication requires strengthening traders. The higher is the merchant's education, turnover, the high level of profit. During the pandemic, the afternoon market remains busy with shopping at the market. But still with health protocols, such as wearing masks and washing hands provided by the regency government. And also the Pamekasan community keeps their distance during shopping at the afternoon market to still be able to communicate with others.

From this, it is illustrated that if market managers convey negative information about the impact of revitalization, for example, traders perceive market managers as credible and master revitalization issues. This is because traders think that if managers convey a negative impact after revitalization, traders think they have control over the problem. The market is a public facility which in its provision requires a public decision. Since public decisions are closely related to the democratic process, the development of development communication in the provision of market infrastructure should also pay attention to the typology of democracy that exists in the built market area.

Participatory communication has a positive impact on the quality of communication. In other words, with participatory communication, managers can provide clear, relevant, accurate, and complete information. Participatory communication also has a positive impact on traders' readiness for revitalization. However, participatory communication harms entrepreneurial capacity, thereby reducing its positive impact on traders' readiness with revitalization. Based on this model, several suggestions were made, including that it is communicating, it managers

need to understand the characteristics of traders. Because of the different responses of traders to the communication carried out, in communication managers need to determine certain segments of traders who give positive responses. In this case, it is choosing younger traders as the target audience. Because they are the ones who are expected to pass on their readiness to others.

Strengthening entrepreneurial capacity can be done by strengthening the quality of communication through strengthening the credibility of managers, revitalization messages, participatory communication, and environmental support, among others in the form of business services. Apart from motivational messages, it is also necessary to reinforce messages about the risks of revitalization. From the model above, it can be seen that the development of entrepreneurial capacity is a major factor in shaping traders' readiness to change. Environmental support is important, but this support only contributes positively to the development of traders' readiness to change if they can increase their entrepreneurial capacity. This is because environmental support harms traders' readiness to change.

4. Conclusion

The communication process between managers and traders begins with the market manager's plan to revitalize the market. Dissemination of information about the revitalization plan is carried out using banners, announcement boards, and leaflets. Besides that, a dialogue between managers and traders was carried out. The dialogue went both ways but was less than satisfying. Feedback during dialogue is also low. Likewise, the mutual trust between managers and traders is also low. In reality, participatory communication which is expected to build the readiness of traders is still weak. As a result, traders' readiness to change with revitalization is still low.

Apart from participatory communication, the level of readiness of traders with revitalization is also influenced by the characteristics of traders, the credibility of market managers, messages conveyed during the revitalization process, and environmental support. In reality, the credibility of managers, messages, and participatory communication is low, so the quality of the resulting communication is also low. This is indicated by the low relevance, clarity, accuracy, and completeness of the information presented. The messages conveyed by market managers to traders are less sharp. This can be seen from the lack of messages about the importance of revitalization, motivation, the statement that revitalization is the right program, and the lack of delivery of messages about risks. These messages are conveyed by credible information sources.

Strengthening the credibility of market managers as a source of messages needs to be done by strengthening internal communication so that coordination between message sources in informal dialogue is in line with message sources in informal dialogue. To build a dialogue with traders, managers can take advantage of managers who are familiar and have attractiveness among traders. This can be done after the source of the message has the expertise that is expected to be obtained from the internal communication built by the manager.

Reference

- Alfianita E, Wijaya AF, Siswidiyanto. (2015). *Revitalization of Traditional Markets in the Perspective of Good Governance: A Study in the Afternoon Market in Pamekasan Regency*. Journal of Public Administration.
- Simanjuntak P. (2017). *Introduction to Humans Resource of is Economics*. Jakarta: Pustaka Setia, p. 185

- Meredith GG, (2018). "*Theory and Practice*". Translate. Andre Asparasayogi. Jakarta: PT Pustaka Binaman Pressindo.
- Muhidin SA. (2016). "*Basics of Statistical Methods for Research*". Bandung
- Swing AAK. (2010). "*Analysis of Merchants' Income Before and After the Traditional Market Revitalization Program in Denpasar City*". Bali: PT Pressindo
- Scarborough NM. (2018). "*Introduction to Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management*". (Indonesian Edition) Jakarta. Jakarta (ID): PT. Rineka Cipta.